

EFFECT OF THE NON-LINEAR PROPERTY OF FIBER-MATRIX INTERFACE
ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FIBROUS COMPOSITES

T. Fujii

Osaka City University
Sugimotocho, Sumiyoshi-ku
Osaka 558, Japan

The behavior of shear deformation of fiber matrix interface in composite materials becomes non-linear according to the increase of load and loading rate.

Various patterns are proposed as the non-linear shearing deformation and load relation. For the simplicity of the analytical consideration, the author adopted the following equation:

$$S = k (dQ/dx)^m ,$$

where

- k: constant
- m: coefficient of non-linearity
- S: shearing force along interface
- Q: load along the fiber
- x: coordinate axis along the fiber.

Considering the equilibrium of displacement and force, the author introduced the next equation:

$$mk(dQ/dx)^{m-1} d^2Q/dx^2 - Q(1/E_f A_f + 1/E_m A_m) = 0$$

where

E_f, A_f : Young's modulus and sectional area of fiber

E_m, A_m : Young's modulus and sectional area of matrix.

This equation is solved under the condition of

$$x = 0; \quad Q = P$$

$$x = \pm(1/2)\ell, \quad Q = 0$$

where

ℓ : length of fiber.

The results of the analysis show that the distribution of interface shear stress varies according to the non-linearity of shearing deformation property. That is, larger the non-linearity, the distribution becomes more uniform and smaller the non-linearity, the distribution becomes concentrated one.

The experimental results of strength properties under static and impact loadings of glass fiber reinforced plastics are examined and above mentioned consideration are applied to the interpretation of the experimental results of strength tests of these materials.